

Pyrimido-thiadiazines. Part II.

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Received 21 October 1970.

Gakhar, Modi and Chander¹ reported the synthesis of hitherto unknown ring system pyrimido-thiadiazines with various substituents in position 3 only. Here the work has been extended to the synthesis of some more pyrimido-thiadiazines (IV) with various substituents in positions 2 as well as 3 of the thiadiazine ring. The synthesis has been achieved by the condensation of 1-amino-2-mercapto 4,4,6-trialkyl 1H,4H pyrimidines²(I) with various α -phenyl α -haloketones (II).

Figure 1.

Unlike the previously reported¹ pyrimido-thiadiazines, the intermediate (III) in the present case could not be isolated. This is evident by the absence of I.R. absorption peak of C = O in the 1730–1690 cm^{-1} region and failure of the product to form any DNP. Between IV and V, structure IV is apparently supported by the absence of N–H band in 3500–3200 cm^{-1} region.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 6,8,8-trimethyl 2,3-diphenyl 2H,8H pyrimido(2,1-b) (1,3,4)thiadiazine (IV) : A solution of α -bromo α -phenylacetophenone (2.75 g.) in ethanol (15 ml.) was mixed with a solution of 2-mercapto 4,4,6-trimethyl 1H,4H pyrimidine (1.71 g.) in 75 ml. of the same solvent and the mixture refluxed on a steam bath for 6½ hrs. The alcohol was distilled off and the residue was crystallised from alcohol-ethylacetate mixture.

TABLE
Data on Pyrimido (2,1-b)(1,3,4)thiadiazines (IV)

S.No.	Pyrimidine used(I)	Ar'	IV			Yield %	m.p. °C	M.F.	Analytical results	
			R'	R''	R'''				Found %	Reqd. %
1.	R' = R'' = R''' = CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	78	255	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ BrN ₃ S	N,	9.36 9.81
2.	-do-	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	70	220	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ BrClN ₃ S	N,	9.34 9.08
3.	-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	75	260	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ BrN ₃ S	C,	60.20 59.73
									H,	5.80 5.43
									N,	9.82 9.50
4.	R' = R'' = CH ₃ , R''' = Et	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	71	222	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ BrN ₃ S	N,	9.28 9.50
5.	-do-	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	62	226	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ BrClN ₃ S	N,	8.79 8.81
6.	-do-	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	65	248	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ BrN ₃ S	N,	9.61 9.21

Other 2-mercapto 4,4,6-trialkyl pyrimidines were condensed with various α -phenyl α -haloketones under similar conditions. The data regarding their yields, m.p., solvent for crystallisation and analytical results are noted in the table.

The authors are thankful to M/s B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar of the Chemistry Department, for carrying out the analysis of these compounds.

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